

RE: Expecting your Payment: AG-MRW-19-0545

American Journal of Biomedical Science & Research <agri@biomedscience.us>

Thu 1/9/2020 7:21 PM

To: 'Mattan Schlomi' <mattanschlomi@aol.com>;

Cc: 薛馬坦 <mshelomi@ntu.edu.tw>;

Importance: High

Dear Dr. Schlomi Mattan,

Start each day with great hope.

We are waiting for your payment from past couple of weeks, can I know the status of it so that we can update to our higher authorities. If you process the payment then we can process the payment for third party services and then we can activate DOI, we can index your article in online repositories.

Please track the below link to make online payment as per your economic strategy of \$979 only instead of \$1179

<https://biomedgrid.com/pay-online.php>

Hope this is fine for you and let you me know your decision behind this.

Await your contribution.

Regards,

Catherine Nichols

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